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CONSTRUCTION AND VALIDATION OF TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCALE (TES) FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT :

Present research task is a process of standardization of self made research tool named 'Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES)' to analyze the effectiveness of teaching process. Total 6 dimensions were identified and 76 statements were drafted for pre-tryout and after the clearance of six educational experts 60 items were finalized in which, 32 items were favourable and 28 items were unfavourable. Against each item there are five responses as Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. For the purpose of tryout, the drafted scale was administered among 148 secondary school teachers of 10 secondary schools of district Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh. After item analysis, 38 items were selected to finalize the Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES). The reliability of developed Teaching Effectiveness Scale was 0.943 with Spearman Brown Prophecy formula. The validity of tool was also satisfactory according educational experts.

KEYWORDS: Construction, Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES), teaching process.

INTRODUCTION

The development of a nation depends upon the standard of their educational system. Education plays a vital and crucial role in reforming and strengthening the society and is directly responsible to the development of a nation. It is an instrument which is used to change the social, economic, cultural and political system of the country. Kothari Commission (1964-66) rightly mentioned that, "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms. This, we believe, is no more rhetoric. In a world based on science and technology, it is education that determines the level of prosperity, welfare and security of the people." So a teacher plays a vital and crucial role in enhancing the classroom atmosphere, their teaching learning process, interaction, control and human relations. "Teaching" is the process of carrying out those activities that experience has shown to be effective in getting students to learn. It is the specialized application of knowledge, skills and attributes designed to provide unique service to meet the educational needs of individual and society. "Effectiveness" in educational aspect, is a term that was developed to provide a more contained definition than notions of 'good' or 'quality' education. It relates to the idea of examining effectiveness at different levels of an education system. Teaching effectiveness is a contested and value-laden concept. It is generally referred to in terms of a focus on student outcomes and the teacher behaviours and classroom processes that promote better student outcomes.

TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS

According to Jackson (1968), teaching is largely an occupation in which teachers function both within their classroom and as a member of the larger school organization, something that has been identified for teachers as a dual allegiance to both the school and students. Firestone & Bader (1991) mentioned that teaching is seen as a rational activity and teachers are seen as adaptable to the new theories and external circumstances. While, Haris et al. (2007) stated that effectiveness is the degree to which workers produce outcomes related to the objectives of their organizations. They also mentioned that effectiveness is “intermediate outcomes” that are indirectly related to the organization’s main objectives and indicative of the quality of the work environment. McKeachie (1979) described that teaching effectiveness is the degree to which one has facilitated student achievement of educational goals. Aregbeyen (2010) defines effective teaching as the process of making student learning possible, promote engagement and discussion, concern and respect for students and maximizing students’ academic achievement. For Jahangiri et al. (2008) it is the extent to which the teaching activity fulfils its intended purpose, function and goals.

Teaching effectiveness is important because it helps student learning. It has become even more important as the emphasis on equality in education has increased. Effective teaching does not occur by chance. Effective teaching has become good at what they do because they evaluate their practice. Teaching effectiveness can be understood by studying the models of teaching that define, effective teachers. One must know a definite set of behaviours which are used by an effective teacher in his daily teaching practice. These behaviours are deep understanding of curriculum, learning theory and individual differences, planning, classroom instructional strategies and evaluations of student understanding and efficiency with learning results.

Friesen (2009) and Barry (2010) are of opinion that as the world changes and the expectations of education shift to meet these changes, the nature of teaching and of its effectiveness must follow suit. Effective teaching is one such idea. The challenge is how to ensure that these practices are in every teacher’s repertoire of professional practice. Effective teaching is fundamental base of learning from lower to higher level of education. If a teacher teaches in a way that results in high gain of knowledge, then teaching will be effective. Main problem in our country is that the quality of teaching is falling day by day. Our educational system at present juncture is producing only educated crowd with low quality because our teacher and teaching methods are at low level. In order to overcome this crisis first step would be to measure teaching effectiveness.

Measuring teaching effectiveness is important because the evidence produced will be used for major decisions about our future in academics. There are two types of decisions to improve teaching, first is formative decision to plan and revise our teaching semester after semester. Second is summative decisions, that are rendered by administrators or colleagues at different points in time to determine whether we have a future. These decisions have an impact on the quality of our professional life. The various sources of evidence for teaching effectiveness may be employed for either formative or summative decisions or both.

In the present purpose teaching effectiveness refers to the preparation and planning for teaching, psychological basis of implementing instructions in classroom, appropriate use of teaching skills, knowledge of subject matter, teacher characteristics, and classroom management. In the context of above view this study is an attempt to construct and standardize a “Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES)”.

CONSTRUCTION OF THE TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCALE

The research literature related to construction of Teaching Effectiveness Scale was consulted thoroughly. Different dimensions of teaching effectiveness were identified. After review of various tools related to teaching effectiveness following dimensions of teaching effectiveness have been identified:

DIMENSIONS

- Preparation and planning for teaching - Teaching objectives, introduction, specific learning activities, suitable techniques, realistic timeline, and lesson plan.
- Psychological basis of implementing instructions in classroom - Freedom of expression and independence of choice, individual differences, student background, mental status, motivating learners by reinforcing,

generation gap, a safe and relaxed atmosphere in the class.

- Appropriate use of teaching skills - Teaching learning material, assessment and evaluations, use of black board, suitable examples, provide variety of learning opportunities and use of aids or others teaching skills.
- Knowledge of subject matter - Complete hold on the subject, Up to date subject knowledge, proper vocabulary and discourse specific knowledge.
- Teacher characteristics - Understand duty and responsibility, knowledge of teaching science, regular and punctual, good communication skills, emotionally stable, knowledge of curriculum and standards, a good sense of humour and focus on dressing.
- Classroom management - Effective classroom behaviour, classroom expectations, clear rules and procedure, consequence of misbehaviour, student feedback and reinforcement.

PRE-TRYOUT OF THE DRAFT TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS SCALE (TES):

Items related to above dimensions were written and necessary editing was done by the researcher. A total of 76 statements were drafted for pre-tryout considering all dimensions of teaching effectiveness dimensions. These items were shown to various experts for suggestions in which some items were modified and some of them were dropped. A total of 60 items were selected out of which 32 statements were favourable and 28 statements were unfavourable.

The distribution of the selected items of the draft teaching effectiveness scale is given in the Table- 1.

Table 1: Distribution of the Selected Statements of the Draft Teaching Effectiveness

Dimensions	Favourable Items	Unfavourable Items	No. of Favourable Items	No. of Unfavourable Items	Total
Preparation and planning for Teaching	1,2,5,7,10	3,4,6,8,9	5	5	10
Psychological basis of implementing instructions in classroom	11,12,15,16,19	13,14,17,18,20	5	5	10
Appropriate use of Teaching Skills	21,22,25,26,27,29	23,24,28,30	6	4	10
Knowledge of subject matter	31,34,35,38,40	32,33,36,37,39	5	5	10
Teacher characteristics	41,42,45,46,50	43,44,47,48,49	5	5	10
Classroom Management	51,52,55,56,59,60	53,54,57,58	6	4	10
Total			32	28	60

The final draft was prepared by arranging the selected items in random manner in a single format. Statements showing both favourable and unfavourable nature have been formulated keeping in view all the dimensions. Against each item, there are five responses- Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The response with which the subject agrees is to be ticked by the subject. The scoring keys for favourable and unfavourable statements against five responses were determined as given in the Table-2.

Table- 2: Scoring key for the Responses

Nature of Items	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
Favourable	5	4	3	2	1
Unfavourable	1	2	3	4	5

Necessary instructions have been attached with the scale. To determine the time limit, the draft scale was administered upon 10 secondary teachers of Bareilly district and it was found that they took 30 minutes in average to respond to all the items. So, 30 minutes was fixed as time limit for responding the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES).

Tryout of the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES)

For the purpose of the try out, the draft scale was administered to 148 secondary teachers of 10 secondary schools of Bareilly district. The schools for tryout were selected by using purposive sampling and all the teachers of the selected schools were included in the sample. Necessary instructions were prepared and included in the beginning of the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale. Oral instructions were also provided whenever necessary. The time limit fixed for the completion of the responses was 30 minutes. The scoring procedure described earlier was followed in tryout of the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale.

Administration of the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES)

The procedure followed in administering the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES) has been described below:

- a) A good rapport between the investigator and the respondents was established by initiating some friendly discussion.
- b) Proper sitting arrangement was made and the draft Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES) was distributed to respond. Teachers were requested to read the instructions carefully. Necessary oral instructions were also provided for their convenience. After 30 minutes all the responded draft teaching effectiveness scales were collected.

ITEM ANALYSIS

The responded draft Teaching Effective Scale (TES) of 148 teachers was scored by using the scoring process as mentioned earlier and then arranged in an order from the highest score to the lowest score. Then 27% (i.e. 40 teachers) of the teachers from the top and 27% (i.e. 40 teachers) of teachers from the bottom were taken apart. Thus two groups, viz. high and low scoring groups were formed. The mean and standard deviation for each individual item by high scoring group and low scoring group were computed. The difference between the mean scores obtained by the high scoring group and low scoring group on a particular item was found out using 't'-test. The t-values were found out by using the formula- $t = \frac{M1 - M2}{O.D}$. Items having t-value > 2.58 and < -2.58 were then identified. Out of 60 items 38 items had t-values greater than 2.58. Distribution of the 38 items according to different dimensions is shown in the Table-3.

Table-3

Dimensions	Favourable Items	Unfavourable Items	No. of Favourable Items	No. of Unfavourable Items	Total
Preparation and planning for Teaching	1,2,7,10	3,4,6,8,9	4	5	9
Psychological basis of implementing instructions in classroom	11,12,19	17,18	3	2	5
Appropriate use of Teaching Skills	25,26,27,29	24,28	4	2	6
Knowledge of subject matter	35,40	32,36,39	2	3	5
Teacher characteristics	41,42,45,46	43,44,47,49	4	4	8
Classroom Management	51,52,56	53,54	3	2	5
Total			20	18	38

Reliability of the Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES)

For calculating the reliability of the developed tool Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES), Split Half Reliability method was used. The score obtained was divided into two equal halves. Odd- even method was used to split the test in to two halves. Then, the coefficient of correlation between these two parts of the test was calculated using the formula of product moment co- efficient of correlation which showed the reliability of the half- test. It was found to be 0.892.The coefficient of reliability of the whole test was then estimated by using Spearman- Brown Prophecy Formula and the reliability of the full test was found to be 0.943. It shows that the developed tool of Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES) was a reliable tool.

Validity of the Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES)

To determine the validity of the Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES), the investigator sent the developed Teaching Effectiveness Scale (TES) to a number of experts seeking judgment regarding the coverage of the construct and it was found satisfactory.

CONCLUSION

The reliability of the scale was found as .943, which is a satisfactory one for such qualitative research. Thus, the Teaching Effectiveness Scale has been prepared for the final administration.

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